

Strain Rate and Temperature Effects on the Nonlinear Behavior of Woven Composites

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Abstract

A polymer-based woven composite was selected and has been characterized using off-axis composite specimens at different strain rates and temperature. A strain rate–temperature equivalence principle is introduced to describe the nonlinear behavior of selected composites. Experimental data shows the validation of the proposed method. An application of comparing the large-strain constitutive theory for describing the nonlinear behavior of woven composites under dynamic loading and the strain rate–temperature equivalence methodology for experiment implementation was presented.

1 Introduction

Many structure applications of composite materials incorporate woven fiber architectures. These materials have very different response to uniaxial loading in different directions relative to the principle fiber directions that can be modeled by the large-strain constitutive theory [1-4]. They also have a strong dependency on strain rate and temperature. The evolution of stiffness and strength of the composite materials subject to different time period and temperature during creep or fatigue process has been investigated and showed a time-temperature equivalent [5]. However, most of the studies focus on the effect of evaluated temperature and its relation with the room temperature in a long-term deformation. The aim of this study was to investigate the relation of composite materials behavior between low temperature quasi-static conditions with the room temperature high strain rate conditions.

In this study, a plain-weave vinyl ester composite material was selected and a number of different strain rate and temperature tensile tests of off-axis coupon specimens were conducted. Comparison of composite nonlinear behavior under different strain rate and temperature indicated that there was a strain rate–temperature relationship between them. Two strain rate–temperature equivalence models based on Williams-Landel-Ferry relationship, Monkman-Grant concept and Arrhenius equation were developed to represent the effects of different strain rate and temperature. The stress-strain analysis that involved in comparing the large-strain constitutive theory and the strain rate–temperature equivalent methodology for different strain rates was presented.

2 Experimental

Tensile tests were performed at various strain rates from low (0.0001/s) to moderate (0.01/s) on an Instron™ servo-hydraulic testing machine with a maximum loading capacity of 20,000 lb.; tests were controlled with a digital control loop using Instron™ Fast-Track 8800 software. Data collection was done by Instron Fast-Track 8800 program and a clip gage fabricated by the authors. The room temperature is 26°C and other test temperature was set up in the range of -15°C ~70°C by the cooling and heating chamber system.

The material tested was E-glass/vinyl ester composite, a ten-ply laminated plate configuration as [0°, 90°, 0°, 90°, 0°, 90°, 0°, 90°, 0°, 90°]_s. The thickness of the plate was 0.18 in. Rectangular specimens with gauge length 3in and width 0.75in were cut from the plate in directions of $\theta=0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$ with respect to the outer ply reinforcement direction. There was 1.5 in grip length on both ends of the specimen that yielded the specimen size of 6×0.75×0.18 in with a gauge length of 3 in, as shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Geometry and dimensions of specimen

2.1 Mechanical behavior at different strain rate and temperature

Fig. 2 & 3 show results for one specimen angle at different strain rates. It shows that strain rate dependence is evident in such materials, even for strain rates that differ by only a few orders of magnitude.

Fig. 4 & 5 show results for one strain rate of specimens under different temperature. It shows high nonlinear stress-strain relationships that strongly relate to different temperature.

3 Model for Strain Rate and Temperature Effects

From the test data, it can be seen that different temperature has the similar effects on the nonlinear behavior of woven composite at a fixed strain rate. It gives us the idea that temperature and strain rate may have an equivalent effect on the composite materials behavior.

3.1 Constituent Behavior Model

From the test data we can get the empirical model of the strain rate and temperature effects as follows:

$$E = B_1 \times \log \dot{\epsilon} + C_1 \tag{1}$$

$$\sigma_b = B_2 \times \log \dot{\epsilon} + C_2$$

and

$$E_m = E_m(T_0) + D(T_0 - T) \quad \sigma_b = \sigma_b(T_0) + k(T_0 - T) \tag{2}$$

Where $E, \dot{\epsilon}, \sigma_b, T$ Represent the elastic modulus, strain rate, strength and temperature.

Fig.6 Variation of the composite strength Vs strain rate

Fig.7 Variation of the composite strength Vs temperature

3.2 Monkman-Grant model

For the relationship between time to failure and strain rate, there is a simple and widely used equation, usually known as Monkman-Grant equation as:

$$t_b \cdot \left(\dot{\epsilon} \right)^m = C_1 \tag{3}$$

Where t_b is the failure time and m is a constant, C_1 is a material constant. Fig. 9 shows this relationship.

Fig.8 Variation of the composite time to failure Vs strain rate

Fig.9 30° specimen test data at different strain rate and temperature

4 Model for Strain Rate and Temperature Equivalence

From the above sections, it can be seen that mechanical properties of woven composite materials are a function of strain rate and temperature. The equivalence between strain rate effects and the temperature effect on the same state of materials can be proposed for such materials. This can be done through

equation of (1) to (3). The objective would be to specify the equivalent temperature, T , for a strain rate, or inversely, to specify the equivalent strain rate for a specified temperature T .

4.1 LWF Approach

From equation (1) we can get

$$\begin{aligned} E &= b_1 \times \log \dot{\epsilon} + c_1 \\ \sigma_b &= b_2 \times \log \dot{\epsilon} + c_2 \\ (b_i &= -\frac{B_i}{m}, c_i = \frac{B_i}{m} \log C_2 + C_i, i = 1, 2 \dots n) \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By combining equation (3) and (4) we can get:

$$\begin{aligned} \log \dot{\epsilon}_T &= \log \dot{\epsilon}_{T_0} + k(T_0 - T) \\ (k &= \frac{D_2}{b_2}) \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

4.2 Attherrius Equation Approach

Attherrius Equation

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \exp\left(\frac{\Delta H}{2.303GT}\right) \tag{6}$$

Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \log \dot{\epsilon}_T &= \log \dot{\epsilon}_{T_0} + k_a \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0}\right) \\ (k_a &= -\frac{\Delta H}{2.303Gm}) \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$T = \left[k_a \log \left(\frac{\dot{\epsilon}_T}{\dot{\epsilon}_{T_0}} \right) + \frac{1}{T_0} \right]^{-1} \tag{8}$$

Where, T and T_0 represent different temperature in absolute temperature unit.

5. Validation of strain rate and temperature equivalent

By comparing the data shown in Fig. 2 to 7 we can get Fig. 9 as below.

It can be found that test data of strain rate at 0.0001/s in $T=26(C$ is almost identical to strain rate at 0.01/s in $T=50(C$. Based on this observation and equation (7) we can get the value of k_a EMBED Equation.DSMT4 k_a is -0.000124 . If we want to get the equivalent test in temperature $T=26(C$ and strain rate at 0.01/s, we can set the test strain rate at 0.0001/s and use the same k_a EMBED Equation.DSMT4 k_a value in equation (8) to get the temperature, which turns out to be $T=5(C$. The validation test result is shown in Fig.10

6. Application of the strain rate and temperature equivalent

The rate dependent nonlinear behavior of woven composite can be modeled by constitutive equation as the prior work [1-3]. Using that model we can predict the nonlinear behavior of the composite at a high strain rate condition. But it is usually difficult to get accurate composite materials behavior in high strain rate through experiment in order to validate the model prediction. By using the strain rate and temperature equivalent concept we can to overcome this difficulty.

Fig. 11 shows the comparison of constitutive model prediction at strain rate 10/s of room temperature and the model calculated equivalent experiment condition data at strain rate 0.01/s of T= -12(C. It shows a good agreement.

7. Conclusion

Tensile tests were conducted on off-axis woven glass reinforced vinyl ester composite laminate specimens with different strain rates and temperature. Effects of strain rate and temperature to the nonlinear material behavior were analyzed. It shows that quasi-static test at low temperature has a similar nonlinear response behavior as the high strain rate at room temperature. The proposed method based on LWF and Attherrius equations can be used for describing the strain rate and temperature equivalence.

Validation of the model was conducted through the test data and showed a good agreement with the model prediction. A useful application of the proposed equivalent model was also discussed. Continuing efforts focus on modeling the structural response of composites and laminates subjected to general dynamic loading and environmental conditions.

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